

IKKINCHI TUR PARABOLIK-GIPERBOLIK TIPDAGI TENGLAMA UCHUN CHEGARAVIY MASALA HAQIDA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20594940>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ikkinchi tur buzilish chizig'iga ega bo'lgan parabolik-giperbolik tipdagi tenglama uchun nolokal C_p masala yechimining bir qiymatli yechilishi ayrim shartlar asosida isbotlangan va parabolik va giperbolik sohalar tomonidan $y=0$ buzilish chizig'ida berilgan funksiyalar orasidagi funksional bog'lanishlar olingan hamda C_p masala yechimining yagonaligi va mavjudligi isbotlangan.

Kalit so'zlar. parabolik-giperbolik, funksional, nolokal, buzilish chizig'i.

Аннотация. В данной статье доказано однозначное решение нелокальной C_p задачи для параболично-гиперболического уравнения с разломом второго порядка при определенных условиях, $y=0$ получены функциональные связи между функциями, заданными параболической и гиперболической областями на разломе, и доказаны единственность и существование C_p решения задачи.

Ключевые слова: параболически-гиперболический, функциональный, нелокальный, линия разлома.

Abstract. In this article, the single-valued solution of a nonlocal C_p problem for a parabolic-hyperbolic equation with a second-order fault line is proved under certain conditions, and $y=0$ functional connections between the functions given by the parabolic and hyperbolic domains on the fault line are obtained, and the uniqueness and existence of the solution C_p of the problem are proven.

Ключевые слова: параболически-гиперболический, функциональный, нелокальный, линия разлома.

KIRISH. Buzilish chizig'iga ega bo'lgan aralash tipdagi tenglamalar uchun qo'yilgan chegaraviy masalalar yechish hozirgi paytda xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalardagi asosiy rivojlangan yo'nalishlardan biridir. Buning sabablaridan bir tomoni bu tenglamalarni amaliyotga qo'llanilishi bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan esa nazariy jihatdan bu tenglamalarga qo'yilgan masalalarni yechilishidir.

Quyidagi tenglamani qaraymiz:

$$0 = \begin{cases} xu_{xx} + \alpha_0 u_x - u_y, & x > 0, \quad y > 0, \\ u_{xx} - (-y)^m u_{yy}, & x > 0, \quad y < 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda

$$0 < \alpha_0 < 1 + 2\beta < 1, \quad 2\beta = \frac{m}{m-2}, \quad 0 < m < 1. \quad (2)$$

Quyida (1) ko‘rinishdagi ikkinchi tur buzilish chizig‘iga ega bo‘lgan parabolik-giperbolik tipdagi tenglama uchun C_p masala yechimining bir qiymatli yechilishi isbotlangan.

(1) tenglama uchun C_p masalasini qo‘yilishi

D orqali $x > 0, y > 0$ bo‘lganda $x=0, x=1, y=1$ mos ravishda to‘g‘ri chiziqlarda yotgan AA_0, BB_0, A_0B_0 kesmalar va $x > 0, y < 0$ bo‘lganda esa (1)

tenglamaning $AB: y=0, 0 < x < 1, AC: x - \frac{2}{2-m}(-y)^{\frac{2-m}{2}} = 0, BC: x + \frac{2}{2-m}(-y)^{\frac{2-m}{2}} = 1$ xarakteristikalari bilan chegaralangan sohani belgilaymiz(1-chizma).

1-chizma.

Quyidagicha belgilashlar kiritamiz:

$$J = \{(x, y): 0 < x < 1, y = 0\},$$

$$D_1 = D \cap \{x > 0, y > 0\},$$

$$D_2 = D \cap \{x > 0, y < 0\},$$

$$D = D_1 \cup D_2 \cup J,$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \pm 0} u(x, y) = \tau^\pm(x), (x, 0) \in \bar{J}, \lim_{y \rightarrow \pm 0} u_y(x, y) = v^\pm(x), (x, 0) \in J \quad (3)$$

$$2\beta = \frac{m}{m-2}, \quad -\frac{1}{2} < \beta < 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\Theta(x) = \left(\frac{x}{2}; -\left(\frac{2-m}{4}(1+x) \right)^{\frac{2}{2-m}} \right), \quad (5)$$

bu yerda $\Theta(x)$ – (1) tenglamani $E(x, 0) \in J$ nuqtasidan chiquvchi EC_1 xarakteristikasi bilan AC xarakteristikasi kesishish nuqtalarining koordinatalari.

C_p masala Quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x, y)$ funksiya topilsin:

$$1) u(x, y) \in C(\bar{D}_1 \cup \bar{D}_2);$$

2) $u(x, y) \in C_{x,y}^{2,1}(D_1)$ bo'lib, D_1 sohada (2.1) tenglamani qanoatlantirsin;

3) $u(x, y) \in R_2$ bo'lib, D_2 sohada (1) tenglamani umumlashgan yechimi bo'lsin;

4) $u(x, y)$ - funksiya quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsin:

$$u|_{AA_0} = \varphi_1(y), \quad u|_{BB_0} = \varphi_2(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (6)$$

$$D_{0x}^{-\beta} \frac{d}{dx} u[\Theta(x)] = a(x)u(x, 0) + b(x), \quad (x, 0) \in J,$$

(7)

5) $u_y \in C(D_1 \cup J) \cap C(D_2 \cup J)$ bo'lib, J buzilish chizig'ida quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{y \rightarrow -0} u(x, y) &= p_1(x) \lim_{y \rightarrow +0} u(x, y) + q_1(x), \quad (x, 0) \in \bar{J}, \\ \lim_{y \rightarrow -0} u_y(x, y) &= p_2(x) \lim_{y \rightarrow +0} u_y(x, y) + q_2(x), \quad (x, 0) \in J, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

ulash sharti bajarilsin, bu yerda $\varphi_1(y)$, $\varphi_2(y)$, $a(x)$, $b(x)$, $p_j(x)$, $q_j(x)$ ($j=1,2$)

berilgan funksiyalar bo'lib, quyidagi shartlarni bajarsin:

$$\varphi_j(x) \in C[0,1] \cap C^1(0,1), \quad (j=1,2), \quad (9)$$

$$a(x) \in C^1(\bar{J}), \quad b(x) \in C^1(0,1], \quad (10)$$

$$p_2(x) < 0, \quad \forall x \in \bar{J}, \quad a(x)p_1(x) \geq 0, \quad \forall (x, 0) \in \bar{J}, \quad (11)$$

$$p_j(x), q_j(x) \in C(\bar{J}) \cap C^2(J), \quad (j=1,2), \quad (12)$$

$b(x)$ funksiya $x \rightarrow 0$ da $-\beta$ darajadan kichik cheksizlikka intiladi, $x \rightarrow 1$ da esa chegaralangan. $D_{0x}^\alpha[\cdot]$ - α kasr tartibli integro-differensial operator bo'lib, $\Theta(x)$ - (5) formula orqali aniqlanadi (1-chizma).

Parabolik soha tomonidan $y=0$ buzilish chizig'ida olingan $\tau^+(x)$ va $\nu^+(x)$ funksiyalar orasidagi funksional bog'lanish

D_1 sohada quyidagi tenglamani qaraymiz:

$$xU_{xx} + \alpha_0 U_x - U_y = 0, \quad 0 < \alpha_0 < 1. \quad (13)$$

(2), (3) va (6) shartlarga hamda parabolik tipdagi tenglamaning xossalariga ko'ra (13) tenglamaga $y \rightarrow +0$ limitga o'tamiz va quyidagi masalani hosil qilamiz:

$$x \tau^{+''}(x) + \alpha_0 \tau^{+'}(x) = \nu^+(x), \quad (x, 0) \in J, \quad (14)$$

$$\tau^+(0) = \varphi_1(0) = 0, \quad \tau^+(1) = \varphi_2(0). \quad (15)$$

Endi (14) va (15) masalani yechishga kirishamiz. Buning uchun (14) differensial tenglamaning umumiy yechimini topamiz:

Ushbu

$$x \tau^{+\prime\prime}(x) + \alpha_0 \tau^{+\prime}(x) = 0 \quad (16)$$

bir jinsli differensial tenglamani umumiy yechimini izlaymiz:

(16) tenglamaga $z(x) = \tau^{+\prime}(x)$ belgilash kiritib, uni quyidagi

$$xz' + \alpha_0 z = 0 \quad (17)$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz va yechamiz:

$$x \frac{dz}{dx} = -\alpha_0 z$$

$$\frac{dz}{z} = -\alpha_0 \frac{dx}{x}$$

ikkala tomonini integrallab

$$\ln|z| = -\alpha_0 \ln|x| + \ln|C_1| = \ln|C_1 x^{-\alpha_0}|$$

ni hosil qilamiz. Bundan

$$z = C_1 x^{-\alpha_0}$$

ni olamiz. Belgilashga ko'ra esa

$$\tau^{+\prime}(x) = C_1 x^{-\alpha_0}$$

yoki

$$\tau^+(x) = \frac{C_1 x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} + C_2 \quad (18)$$

ni hosil qilamiz. (18) formula (16) tenglamaning umumiy yechimidir.

Endi o'zgarmasni variatsiyalash usulidan foydalanib, (14) tenglamaning umumiy yechimini topamiz. Buning uchun (18) ifodani ushbu

$$\tau^+(x) = \frac{C_1(x)x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} + C_2(x) \quad (19)$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz.

(19) ni (14) ga qo'yib, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{C_1'(x)x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} + C_2'(x) = 0, \\ C_1'(x)x^{1-\alpha_0} = v^+(x), \end{cases}$$

yoki

$$\begin{cases} C_1'(x) = x^{\alpha_0-1} v^+(x), \\ C_2'(x) = -\frac{v^+(x)}{1-\alpha_0}. \end{cases}$$

Bundan esa, noma'lum $C_1(x)$ va $C_2(x)$ funksiyalarni quyidagicha topamiz:

$$\begin{cases} C_1(x) = \int_0^x t^{\alpha_0-1} v^+(t) dt + C_3, \\ C_2(x) = -\frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^x v^+(t) dt + C_4 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

(20) ni (19) ga qo'yib, (14) tenglamaning umumiy yechimini olamiz:

$$\tau^+(x) = \frac{x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^x t^{\alpha_0-1} v^+(t) dt + \frac{C_3 x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} + C_4 - \frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^x v^+(t) dt \quad (21)$$

Endi noma'lum C_3 va C_4 o'zgarmlarni topish uchun (21) umumiy yechimga (15) shartni qanoatlantiramiz:

$$\tau^+(0) = C_4 = 0,$$

$$\tau^+(1) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha_0-1} v^+(t) dt + \frac{C_3}{1-\alpha_0} - \frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^1 v^+(t) dt = \varphi_2(0).$$

Bundan, noma'lum C_3 va C_4 o'zgarmlarni ushbu

$$\begin{cases} C_4 = 0, \\ C_3 = \int_0^1 v^+(t) dt - \int_0^1 t^{\alpha_0-1} v^+(t) dt + (1-\alpha_0)\varphi_2(0) \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

ko'rinishda aniqlaymiz.

(22) ni (21) ga qo'yamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau^+(x) &= \frac{x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^x t^{\alpha_0-1} v^+(t) dt + \frac{x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^1 \left(1-t^{\alpha_0-1}\right) v^+(t) dt - \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^x v^+(t) dt + x^{1-\alpha_0} \varphi_2(0) = \\ &= \frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^x \left(x^{1-\alpha_0} t^{\alpha_0-1} + x^{1-\alpha_0} - t^{\alpha_0-1} x^{1-\alpha_0} - 1 \right) v^+(t) dt + \\ &\quad + \frac{x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} \int_x^1 \left(1-t^{\alpha_0-1}\right) v^+(t) dt + x^{1-\alpha_0} \varphi_2(0) = \\ &= \frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \int_0^x \left(x^{1-\alpha_0} - 1 \right) v^+(t) dt + \frac{x^{1-\alpha_0}}{1-\alpha_0} \int_x^1 \left(1-t^{\alpha_0-1}\right) v^+(t) dt + x^{1-\alpha_0} \varphi_2(0). \end{aligned}$$

Shunday qilib, (14) (15) masalaning yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishda topamiz:

$$\tau^+(x) = \int_0^1 G(x,t) v^+(t) dt + x^{1-\alpha_0} \varphi_2(0), \quad (x, 0) \in \bar{J}, \quad (23)$$

bu yerda

$$G(x,t) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha_0} \begin{cases} x^{1-\alpha_0} (1-t^{\alpha_0-1}), & 0 \leq x \leq t, \\ x^{1-\alpha_0} - 1, & t \leq x \leq 1. \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

(24) formula bilan aniqlangan $G(x,t)$ funksiya bir jinsli (14), (15) masalasining Grin funksiyasi bo'ladi.¹

Demak, (23) formula D_1 parabolik sohadan J buzilish chizig'ida olingan $\tau^+(x)$ va $\nu^+(x)$ funksiyalar orasidagi birinchi funksional bog'lanish.

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